

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: MGED

COURSE CODE: ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERCK

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ESSAY WRITING AND THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE EXPRESSON

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic essay writing requires a thorough understanding and proper use of the English language. The course- international academic and professional paper writing has been for me an eye-opener as I have learnt that even though the English language appears to be spoken and written in the same way universally, there are many nuances, inflection and influences that create some differences in the way English is spoken and written in the United Kingdom and the United States of America. These differences only serve to make the art of written and spoken expression in English, a matter of choice and style. I have also come to understand that within this freedom of choice of expression, there is also standardization of the two varieties of English.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING AND STYLE GUIDES OR RULES OF STYLE

Before I delve into exploring the differences between UK and US English and how they influence the choice and style of writing an Academic Essay, I would like to define what an Essay is. The Curtin University Online Learning Centre defines an essay as follow:

An extended piece of writing that presents and supports a thesis or proposition. The word 'essay' derives from the Latin word 'exagium,' meaning the presentation of a case. When you write an essay, you are

making a case for the validity of a particular point of view, analysis, interpretation, or set of facts or procedures.

Essay writing, especially as it concerns the writing of an academic essay, requires the presentation of an Argument for or against a case or a subject matter. The EUCLID 2015 ACA-401 Coursepack (similar to Curtin University Learning Centre) says an essay is an academic exercise, which aims to persuade readers about an idea based on evidence. It goes on to say that the writer is expected to proffer a thesis statement and an argument, relevant examples, supporting evidence, and information from academic texts in order to answer a question or carry out a task (EUCLID 2015, 1).

Essay writing is made up of elements such as researching and referencing. The writer is also expected to employ both creative thinking and critical thinking within the context of the academic essay. Creative thinking is employed when the writer broadens his or her ideas through brainstorming and mind mapping while critical thinking is employed when the writer narrows down the scope of his or her own his ideas. Mind mapping allows the academic writer to structure his or her ideas in a way that would enable him or her recall those ideas with ease. On the other hand, brainstorming is a discussion amongst members of a group on a subject matter with the aim of generating new ideas or solving problems. The later and the former help the writer to strike a balance in his or her academic essay writing and at the same time. Academic essay writing gives the writer the freedom to use his or her preferred English expression while adhering to various English standardizations and style guides.

a) Standardization

Merriam-Webster's Online Dictionary defines standardizing as "changing (things) so that they are similar and consistent and agree with rules about what is proper and acceptable.

Setting and adopting a standard is aimed at ensuring conformity and the avoidance of deviation. A standard is also aimed at ensuring uniformity. In the use of English for academic essays, I have learnt that there are various universal standards, which help to ensure uniformity. The English language is standardized along the lines of Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE). These give the academic Essay Writer the choice of using and conforming to any of the standard English as long as he or she remains consistent and adheres to the syntactical, semantically and lexical rules and regulation guiding any of the chosen standard English of his or her choice.

What gives rise to standardization of English as we earlier mentioned is the acceptance, by a group of persons, of the nuances, inflections, differences, format, and style of a language. In the case of the English language, the SAE and the SBE are universally the same but are peculiarly different when it comes to certain elements of their Grammar and vocabulary. These expressions and nuances and inflections have been accepted by both UK and US as standards. This is also as a result of the morphing of the English language. History has it that this morphing and standardization was a deliberate exercise aimed at

differentiating the way English is spoken in the United Kingdom and in the United States. An Article published on the website of the British Council says the following:

The British actually introduced the language to the Americas when they reached these lands by Sea between the 16th and 17th Centuries. At that time, spelling had not yet been standardized. It took the writing of the first dictionaries to set in stone how these words appeared. In the UK, the dictionary was compiled by London-based scholars. Meanwhile, in the United States, the lexicographer was a man named Noah Webster. Allegedly, he changed how the words were spelled to make the American version different from the British as a way of showing cultural independence from its mother country (<https://www.britishcouncilfoundation.id/en/english/articles/british-and-american-english>).

The differentiation ranged from grammar differences, vocabulary differences and spelling differences.

The English Language can be said to have morphed into various varieties in the world ranging from what we call in Nigeria “pidgin English” to Patois in the West Indies. It is in light of this linguistic morphology that we have arrived at the UK Standard English and the US Standard English. The change in morphology and codification in the English language is also brought about by many factors ranging from socio-cultural to technological evolution.

Socio-cultural influences on the morphology of the English language (particularly the Standard American English language), come in many forms such as euphemistic references, “equality vocabulary, “politically correct” references, ethnolect Yiddish and ethnic Jewish influences, jargons resulting from changing cultural references, regional variation, identity, stereotyping, obscenities and implied obscenities. These influences on the semantics, syntax, lexis and structure of the English language have also resulted in the further divergence in the two standards.

The impact of these socio-cultural factors is seen in the differences and divergence between the SAE and SBE. These differences are as follows: having the same words but different or additional meaning, having same concept but different terms of expression (barrister vs solicitor which both means lawyer, attorney at law or attorney), different pronunciation with the same meaning (aluminium/aluminum), different spelling but same pronunciation (ax and axe ,cheque and check), same term with different but similar spelling and punctuation (maths and math), and different or additional meaning (a torch in American English could mean a flashlight, electric torch or a flaming torch).

b) Standardization and Style Guide or Rule of Style

EUCLID has its own Standards. Students are allowed to use either the SAE or SBE as long as they remain consistent in their choices. However, EUCLID recommends the use of the SAE for academic essay writing. It also has its own word processing formats both for its response paper and for its main paper. It has several standards by which the essay writer is expected to adhere to and these are outlined on the templates of both its response paper and main paper as part of its style guide or rule of style. Such standards include the Chicago-Turabian style that determine the type of referencing and research methodology to be used in its academic papers. The Chicago style is the style adopted for formatting books and research papers. This style is documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996. These rules of style are both published by the University of Chicago Press. They discuss areas such as preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK vs US for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences, structure, paragraph numbering and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists and much more. Other areas include abbreviations & acronym, capitalization, compound words, emphasis, numbers & date, quotation, Chicago page formatting, title and text page, footnotes, headings and lists, bibliography & tables, table note, Chicago end/footnotes, authors & books, journals & newspapers, reports & papers, references and documents Chicago bibliographies (EUCLID Chicago-Turabian Style Crib Sheet, 1).

The chosen standards and style guide give the writer's work the identity of EUCLID academic Treatise. It also serves as a style guide for the writer so that he is not given the liberty to use just any template or format for his or her academic essays. This customized style guide and template are also adopted in some technical, commercial and business writing. Companies, websites or publication outfits that contract writers have rules of style that the writers are expected to conform to. These styles give their publications unique identities and help them in saving time on formatting of the work.

In the same vein, there are other types of style guides such as The Economist style guide whose guiding principle says that clarity of writing usually follows clarity of thought. So the Guide encourages its users to think about what they want to say and then say it as simply as possible. Other style guides or rules of style include World Health Organization (WHO) rule of style, European Commission rule of style, Harvard University rule of style, and Oxford University rule of style.

i) *Choice and Style*

Whether the EUCLID academic paper writer chooses the SAE or the SBE is a matter of choice and style as long as he or she stays within the ambit of the regulation guiding the use of both standard English styles of expressions. The writer can have the liberty of navigating between synonyms. He or she may make use of short or long sentences

as long as they respect grammatical rules and are clear and coherent. EUCLID however prefers sentences that are not short or not too long and recommends the use of the Standard American English.

ii) *Choice and Convention*

Choice of expression and laid down convention may or may not agree depending on the writer's choice and style. However, it is imperative for the academic writer to keep in mind the fact that the style guide is a convention that cannot be ignored. It is very easy to ramble on but having to adhere to every grammatical rule of the English I chose to express myself with (be it SBE/ SAE and Chicago-Turabian style guide), is teaching me a lot of discipline in the area of academic writing. This may be a challenge to most creative writers who may be required to restrict their styles to other creative fields. According to Euclid University:

Many creative writers eschew the need for a style guide, believing that the ability to follow a Standard English Writing Style should be an innate quality for any Writer. While to a Certain extent this could be argued to be true, a style Guide provides a mean of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output (EUCLID- LIT-101 Review 2015, 7).

Certainly, the course international academic and professional paper writing is showing me that there is a lot more to the English language that meets the eye and that the ability to follow a standard English writing style is not an innate quality for any writer but convention that needs to be studied and learnt for consistency.

3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is the academic writer's job to persuade readers to agree or disagree with an idea through reasoning and argument on his or her thesis statement. In doing these, he or she may wish to make use of supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources. He or she also has the liberty to choose the standard English that would empower him or her to dissect the subject matter. However, he or she is expected to remain within the confined of the EUCLID style guide or rule of style while employing creative and critical thinking in the process of presenting and dissecting his or her thesis statement in an academic essay. This is aimed at giving every EUCLID dissertation the EUCLID identity and maintaining its high standards.

REFERENCES

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